

MARRIAGE AND TRIBAL EDUCATION

***Dr Saroj K Nayak & **Dr Nirupama Nayak**

* Asst Prof (TE), UG CTE, Baripada Mbj Odisha

** Asst Prof (TE) MPC (AUTO) College, Baripada, Mayurbhanj, Odisha

Paper Received On: 20 MAR 2026

Peer Reviewed On: 24 APRIL 2026

Published On: 01 MAY 2026

Abstract

Tribal population is widely distributed throughout the state of Odisha. As per the 2011 census scheduled tribe constitute more than 22.84% of the total population. Out of the 12 tribal dominated districts in Odisha, 9 Districts namely Mayurbhanj, Kendujhar Sundergarh, Kandamal, Gajapati, Karaput, Rayagada, Malkangiri, & Nabarangpur has tribal population more than 50% of the total population. These Districts have Special Development Councils (SDC). Through decades many plans programs policies were adopted for the all round development of the tribal people. Although some appreciable development is seen in various dimensions, the Educational achievement in terms of retention of the tribal people of Odisha is far away from the main Stream. Among so many factors responsible for the low achievement, one may be the early and unplanned marriage of the tribal people. There are various types of marriage prevails in tribal society which permits, allows and respects the liberty of the individuals to take the decision of marriage In this paper sincere efforts were made to study the effect of marriage on the achievement levels of Education in terms of retention. Thirty six cases of early marriage of Tribal's in the Districts of Mayurbhanj were thoroughly studied and causes of early marriage ,effect of the marriage on the Educational achievement level was analyzed and some suggestions were provided to tackle the problems. In the absence of early marriage of the tribal people, the retention rate in the higher education will definitely increase.

INTRODUCTION:

There was no direct program for the tribal people to provide formal education before 1950. With the adaption of constitution, the promotion of Education of the tribal peoples became the responsibility of both the central and state government. The educational deplorable condition of the tribal people can be assessed by fact that according to census data of 1931, only 0.7% tribal people were literate. But due to effect of various initiatives taken by the state and the central Government to promote tribal Education the literacy rate raised to 32.60% in

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1991.and according to census 2011 it became 58.96% .but till it is far away from national literacy rate i.e. 80.89% .

Our region of study Odisha and particularly in the district of Mayurbhanj the literacy rate of the tribal population according to 2011 census data is 52.2% & 53.1% respectively against the overall literary rate of Odisha and Mayurbhanj 73.45% and 63.17% .

Our study was mainly concentrated over Baripada ,Kuliana,Shamakhunta ,G.B Nagar, Kaptipada ,saraskana, Bangriposi, Bisoi,Bahalda,karanjia block of Mayurbhanj. According to the OPEPA,DISE10-11the dropout rate of tribal students of Mayurbhanj is 4.77% as compare to overall dropout of 2.63% in Primary level. As per the household survey conducted in2017 in Mayurbhanj reveals that the dropout rate of tribal students of Mayurbhanj in lower primary level age (6-10yr) is 1%, in upper primary Level (11-14 yr)it is 12% in secondary level (15-16yr) it is 41% .crossing the age of 18yr very few percentage of students reach the higher education institutions in Mayurbhanj .

With the increase of age the rate of dropout among tribal students increase causing a great wastage of the state wealth. The dropout rate of girls is higher than that of the boys. The rate of drop out in primary level of girls is 9.16% as compared to boys 4.61%. Similar trend is observed in secondary and higher secondary level.

There are so many causes for the high rate of dropout among tribal students like,1. Improper school curriculum, medium of instruction,2.Distance of the school from the village,3.Infrastructure problems,4.Healthproblems and inadequate healthcare facility,5.Holiday pattern and schooling time.,6.Interruption of Family friends and relatives,7.economic conditions of the parents ,8.indeferent attitude of the Parents.

Among the above causes of high dropout rate of tribal students one of the most potent cause is early marriage before attaining the legal age. In this research emphasis was put to find out the cause of early child marriage and the consequences on the achievement and attainment in terms of retention.

OBJECTIVES:

1. To identify the causes of early marriage among tribal.
2. The effect of early marriage in educational attainment in terms of retention and level of achievement.
3. To study the consequence of low Educational achievement and retention, in individual and social level.
4. To suggest some curative measure to tackle the problem

LITARETURE REVIEW:

“A child marriage between a boy and girl below 18 years of age will be psychologically stressful including in areas of health, education, economy and decision-making. Child brides face higher rates of domestic violence, maternal mortality and infant mortality,” said the department. The PTM’s initiative assumed huge significance in the wake of the high rate of child marriages reported across the State, especially in tribal areas in the two years of the pandemic. Ranipokhari, a tribal-dominated panchayat in Mayurbhanj district, had alone reported 122 child marriages in 2020 and 2021. Children, especially girl students in residential schools, were reported to have got married when they were sent home during COVID-19 pandemic. Child marriage was one of the reasons that many girls students had not turned up for their matriculation (Standard-X) examination. Even some dropped out in smaller classes as in Class VI. (Satya sundar Barik,The Hindu,July 11,2022,BBSR)

Anthropologists attribute the prevalence of child marriages to the tradition and culture of tribal societies. If an underage girl-and-boy elopes, parents approve of their marriage in haste by taking the community into confidence. In some cases, parents themselves force their children into wedlock.

Child marriage traps underage children in a complicated relationship but girls end up becoming victims of sexual subjugation, drudgery and virtual confinement. At least 7.6 pc of girls in 15-19 age group are already mothers or pregnant in the State which explains why child marriages must go.

Poverty apart, lack of education is responsible for high prevalence of child marriage. Only 26.7 pc women have 10 or more years of schooling which means a third of the women leave studies once they are 15 which prompt parents to marry them off. “Parents go for early marriage of their daughters as they believe girls sitting at home are burden,” Programme Manager of Action Aid Ghasiram Panda said.

A National Commission for Protection of Child Rights (NCPCR) report says trafficking is a major trigger because girls are kidnapped to be forced into marriages. In 2016, at least 162 girls were kidnapped for marriage in Odisha and most reports came from Mayurbhanj, Angul, Kandhamal and Balasore.

However, a number of tribal communities like Kandh, Paraja, Sauras, Juangas and Paudi have resolved not to allow under-age marriages which is a silver lining, Panda said.

The Odisha Government claims that the incidents are on a declining trend - from 45 pc in 1992-93 to 21.3 pc in 2015-16. “We have been conducting gender sensitisation training of

students boys and girls in high schools, colleges and universities besides the officials. We would rope in grass root institutions and monitor them to build community networks and partnerships to curb the practice,” Secretary, Women and Child Development Department Chithra Arumugam says.(Hemanta Kumar Rout,The New Indian Express,15th January,2018)

METHODOLOGY:

The research proceed through qualitative method of interviewing the thirty six early married couples from ten tribal dominated blocks namely Baripada ,Kuliana,Shamakhunta ,G.B Nagar, Kaptipada ,saraskana, Bangriposi, Bisoi,Bahalda,karanjia of Mayurbhanj. Quantitative research methodology was followed in designing questionnaire, analysis and writing up. The data collected from the sample survey by personal contact were tabulated and analyzed to reach the conclusion. The questions were framed after careful literature review and according to the objectives of the research.

RESULTS AND DISSCUSSION:

The findings of the research is summarized in the table given below

Total no of cases	No of cases of under age of Girls	No of cases of under age boys	No of cases of under age of Both	Cause of marriage, Love	Cause of marriage, Premarital Sex	Cause of marriage, Pressure From family	Drop out of Girl	Drop out of Boy	Drop out of Both	The girl is Happy after marriage	The Boy is Happy after marriage	Both are Happy after marriage	Engaged in manual low cost	Financially sound after arriage
36	36	6	6	23	07	05	32	06/06	06	09	02/06	02/06	29	07
	100	16.6	16.6	63.8	19.4	13.8	88.8	100	16.6	25	36.1	36.1	80.	19.4
	%	6%	6%	8%	4%	8%	8%	%	6%	%	1%	1%	55	5%

In the study of only thirty six cases of early marriage of tribal people in the district of Mayurbhanj it was observed that

1. In almost all cases of early marriage, the girl is under age i.e.100% as compared to only16.66% of boys.
2. There are many causes of Early marriage but as stated by the early married couples, they can be categorized as(1) due to love (2),pre marital sex , (3)and others. According to the study 63.88% of early marriage of tribal people are due to love affairs, and as they stated it starts from the participation in group amusements in festive occasions.19.44% cases occurs due to premarital sex and 13.88% due to family pressure and other reason.

3. The dropout rate of girls due to early marriage is 88.88% as compared to male 100%. After early marriage 8-12% girls manage to appear the board examination where the pass rate is very low. So the governments' wealth and endeavor to educate the girl child is wasted to a large amount due to early marriage.

4. Due to inadequate education and insufficient training of life skill, 75% girls become unhappy within few months of early marriage. But 36.11% of boys found to be happy with their life.

5. After marriage in 80.55% boys and girls engage themselves in manual low cost job or become daily labor, but 19.45 % remain financially sound due to the parental property

CAUSES OF EARLY MARRIAGE OF TRIBAL PEOPLE;

The institution of marriage is observed in all human society. It legalizes the sexual relation between male and female, and legitimizes the offspring produced out of this sexual relationship. In tribal societies different types of marriage is seen which provides ample opportunity for the teenager to go for marriage easily. These types are

1. **MARRIAGE BY PROBATION:** in this type of marriage the man is allowed to live with the woman at her parents' house for definite time without marriage.

2. **MARRIAGE BY CAPTURE:** In this type of marriage one tribal man can forcibly marry one girl even without the consent.

3. **MARRIAGE BY TRIAL:** In this type of marriage any brave and courageous tribal man is allowed to marry a girl showing his skill.

4. **MARRIAGE BY PURCHASE:** In this type of marriage the bridegroom's parents pay to the bride's parents.

5. **MARRIAGE BY SERVICE:** In this types of marriage The Bridegrooms serves the father-in-law's house for definite period of times before marriage.

6. **MARRIAGE BY EXCHANGE:** In these types of marriage the families exchange their son and daughter.

7. **MARRIAGE BY ELOPMENT:** In these types of marriage woman and man love each other and instead of refusal of the parents they escape from the village and marry.

8. **MARRIAGE BY INTRUSION:** In this type of marriage the woman takes the initiative and enters into the beloved house tolerating all adversities.

Tribal customs such as Jhikinawa, Baaliphool and traditional live-in arrangements, create opportunities of mingling and socializing among young adolescents. However, this is also a

reason of child marriage among the tribal communities, as lack of awareness about safe sex leads to high incidence of teenage pregnancy and compels them for marriage at an early age. Social practices, education status, traditional norms like getting married at an early age and lack of awareness were some of the reasons behind early marriage.

Due to very low achievement level in study the tribal students could not engage themselves in higher education and always try to escape from the system.

CONSEQUENCES OF EARLY MARRIAGE IN EDUCATION:

The girls are worse affected by early marriage. Marriage and pregnancy also force the girls to drop out from school and are unable to fulfil their aspiration in life.

It is almost impossible for married girls to return to schools as she has to take much household responsibility

Impact on Boys: Boys too get deprived of education and skills and are compelled to get into unskilled low paid jobs at a very young age because of early marriage.

National wealth is wasted by incomplete education of the tribal students.

The incomplete education doesn't give any fruit to the tribal student by which the time spend in the previous study become useless

SUGGESTION:

In order to tackle the problems of early marriage problems along with the existing strategy we should put much emphasis on

1. Mass and individual awareness campaign: As the tribal students mainly the girls are more vulnerable to early marriage, they should be aware about the future problems of the early marriage citing various illustrations. The parents should be provided with proper guidance and counselling regarding the negative impact.
2. Attitudes of the parents need to be positively channelized.
3. Quality primary Education should be provided to each and every tribal child,
4. Child centric education is to be strictly maintained
5. More residential school should be established to accommodate more tribal students
6. Social Security of the tribal students especially of the girl students should be ensured.

CONCLUSION;

Both marriage and Education are important in life. Along with enjoyment marriage brings lot of responsibility in life and in order to handle each situation, huddles of life, education prepares and equipped with all essential ingredients. After completion of education and getting mastery over the required skill for life one should venture for marriage for successful life. In this research it is observed that one of the potent cause of Tribal students drop out from the school and hence the wastage of national wealth is the early marriage. And reversely the high dropout rate is also a potent cause of early marriage. So it is high time to tackle both the issue simultaneously for the high retention rate and all-round development of the tribal people

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